

Numerical Simulations of Turbulent Thermal, Bubble and Hybrid Plumes

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Abstract

To understand the near-field dynamics of blowout plumes such as the one produced by the 2010 Deepwater Horizon oil spill in the Gulf of Mexico, the effects of gas bubbles on turbulent mixing and entrainment are studied via turbulence resolving simulations. We compare the evolution of three plumes where extremely large buoyancy anomalies are produced either thermally (single phase), solely by an imposed gas phase volume fraction, or by a combination of both buoyancy forcings. The plumes, with identical volume, momentum and buoyancy fluxes at the inlet, are released into an environment stratified with a constant temperature gradient. To clarify the first-order effects of dynamically active, dispersed bubbles, we employ a simple model which neglects the momentum of the gas phase while retaining bubble induced buoyancy in the seawater momentum equation. The gas phase is then distinguished by a single, measurable parameter, the slip velocity relative to that of the liquid phase. We find that bubbles, parameterized simply by a constant slip velocity, without any explicit assumptions of direct bubble induced turbulent production, significantly increase turbulent mixing in the plume in agreement with previous experimental results. Examination of mean momenta and turbulent kinetic energy budgets

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shows that the increased turbulence is due to direct modification of the mean profiles of both the momentum and the active scalar fields by the slipping gas phase. The narrowing of the active scalar field in the two-phase flow results in larger direct buoyancy production of turbulent energy at all vertical levels. The turbulence production is, however, primarily mechanical. At modest values of z/D , where the slip velocity is only a small fraction of the liquid phase velocity, slip stretches the mean vertical velocity field producing larger radial gradients and increased conversion of mean to turbulent energy. This first order effect, acting on the mean vertical velocity component and not directly on the turbulence, implies that even relatively small gas volume fractions significantly enhance turbulent mixing with respect to a single phase plume.

Keywords: Multiphase flows, buoyant plumes, deepwater blowouts

1. Introduction

This work, motivated by the 2010 Deepwater Horizon (DwH) incident in the northern Gulf of Mexico, focuses on modeling and simulating the near-field region of flows driven by the extreme buoyancy fluxes typical of deep water oil well blowouts [1]. Deepwater blowout plumes are formed by the sustained point release of a hot, multiphase wellhead mixture through the riser pipe. The resulting buoyancy flux, released into a stratified fluid, was thermally equivalent to $B_0 = \mathcal{O}(1GW)$ in the Deepwater Horizon case [2]. The magnitude of the buoyancy anomaly, sustained over a period of months, and the extremely large range of spatial scales involved (0.5 meter source at 1,500 meter depth) implies that these multiphase plumes are far from realizable laboratory conditions [3]. The extremely large, sustained buoyancy fluxes also imply that the wellhead convection problem has the potential to dynamically alter the larger scale, rotating and stratified environment.

The DwH release underscored the need for rapid and informed response to such events. An integral part of that response is the prediction of both the distribution of hydrocarbon effluent throughout the water column and the eventual

18 form of its expression at the ocean surface. Since the near-field turbulent en-
19 trainment plays a critical role in the evolution of the plume buoyancy, mass
20 and momentum fluxes, understanding and modelling *multiphase* plume dynam-
21 ics in the vicinity of the release is potentially critical to accurate prediction of
22 the near-surface pollution transport problem over of the *last mile*, where the
23 spill encounters the public. The inlet buoyancy flux generates a strongly tur-
24 bulent buoyant plume in which sea water entrained from the environment is
25 mixed with the plume core fluids as they move along the water column. The
26 evolution of the plume is strongly affected by the level of turbulent mixing and
27 entrainment in the near-field with the 'entrainment coefficient' being the main
28 parameter in classic integral solution approaches [4]. It is well-known that the
29 presence of a gas phase changes the turbulent transport properties, with bubble
30 plumes typically exhibiting larger turbulence levels [5], [6]. There are distinct
31 differences in the along-column effluent distribution in single and multiphase
32 cases [7], [8]. The effects of bubbles on turbulent dynamics are studied here by
33 comparing plumes distinguished only by the phase distribution of the (fixed)
34 inlet buoyancy flux, either thermal (single phase) or due to the presence of gas
35 (multiphase).

36 Modeling in complete, accurate detail, the physicochemical dynamics of the
37 high pressure release of hot, multicomponent, multiphase effluent into a strat-
38 ified, turbulent ocean environment is beyond our present theoretical and com-
39 putational abilities. As in the case of the DwH incident, both short and inter-
40 mediate term prediction and analysis of any future event will rely on simplified
41 models for which there is existing literature. How the validity of underlying
42 assumptions and the values of explicit parametrizations in simplified models
43 change when such models are scaled up from the laboratory to the environ-
44 ment requires careful examination of the many physical and chemical processes
45 involved.

46 Given their environmental and industrial importance, buoyant plumes have
47 been the focus of considerable study. Schmidt [9] presented an earlier dimen-
48 sional analysis of thermal plumes, and the problem has attracted the attention

49 of Batchelor [10], Morton [4], Turner [11], [12] and others. Many of these ef-
50 forts represent the depth dependence bulk plume measure, like momentum and
51 buoyancy flux, in terms of the basic system parameters. Turner discusses sev-
52 eral laboratory experiments in support of the scaling laws. List and Imberger
53 [13] is an early reference on plumes in stratified environments, pointing out the
54 creation of intrusion layers. MacDougall [5] performed perhaps the first experi-
55 ments of two phase convective systems, discussing the presence of dual plumes.
56 Classification of bubble plume experiments and observations appear in Lemck-
57 ert and Imberger [8] and Socolofsky and Adams [14], [15]. Classical modeling
58 efforts directed at oil spill prediction have been posed as a Lagrangian problem,
59 in which integral plume measures, like momentum flux and centerline trajectory
60 were computed [16]. These have been tested against laboratory and limited field
61 experiments and have demonstrated skill. In all cases, the equations are closed
62 by relating the turbulent radial flux to the characteristic mean vertical velocity
63 via an entrainment coefficient [4]. Enhanced turbulent mixing of vertical mo-
64 mentum due to multiphase physics is typically modelled by a larger momentum
65 amplification factor, reducing the vertical momentum growth rate in comparison
66 to single phase plumes.

67 The goal of the present work is to understand and quantify, in the context of
68 turbulence resolving simulations, basic physical properties of plumes driven by
69 the extreme values of the expected buoyancy flux in a deepwater blowout. This
70 fills a significant gap in our present knowledge of deep spills, specifically the
71 role played by the gas in increasing the turbulent mixing. The DwH blowout
72 involved both oil and gas escaping from the well head [2]. As a first step, we iso-
73 late the effect of bubbles on the turbulence by considering idealized situations
74 where admittedly important physicochemical phenomena (hydrate formation,
75 dissolution or biodegradation) are neglected and the input buoyancy is due
76 solely to thermal and gas contributions. Given that it is not possible in such
77 incidents to determine the exact proportions of oil and gas involved at specific
78 instances or periods, we explore distinctions in the turbulent behavior of plumes
79 produced by varying the relative importance of the inlet gas buoyancy contri-

80 bution. Such idealized cases are closer to the flow configuration used in most
81 experimental studies of bubble plumes but differ significantly in the magnitude
82 of the inlet buoyancy flux. Moreover, to our knowledge there are no experimen-
83 tal observations of the combined effects of thermal and gas sources. Laboratory
84 experiments of bubble and oil plumes face a number of challenges. Usually the
85 tank size is limited in the vertical direction and the reflection of the plume from
86 the upper boundary can change the flow field significantly. Due to box-filling
87 problems, limited tank size necessarily limits both the inlet oil flux and the
88 overall time scales of experiments. To attain flows that are highly turbulent,
89 nozzle sizes used in the laboratory are typically on the order of a few millime-
90 ters. Even then, the observation period for measurements is typically minutes
91 [17], [18]. It is unclear how representative plumes from such small nozzles are
92 for the real oceanic case. Finally, we are not aware of laboratory experiments of
93 hybrid (bubble and oil) plumes and highly-parameterized models do not allow
94 direct exploration of the details of the turbulent behavior in such cases.

95 Computationally, significant efforts have been devoted to the study of mul-
96 tiphase plumes at oceanographic scales in the context of CO₂ sequestration
97 [19], [20]. These studies emphasize the effects of physico-chemical phenomena
98 on overall plume behavior using standard eddy-viscosity and eddy-diffusivity
99 models to account for turbulent transport. Characterization of the differences
100 in the turbulent mixing between single and multiphase plumes requires explicit
101 resolution of finer scale motions. This is particularly important for plumes where
102 differences in near-field turbulent entrainment processes significantly influence
103 far field behavior and, consequently, the overall distribution of effluents in the
104 water column including the fraction of effluent reaching the ocean surface.

105 While complete spatial and temporal descriptions via Direct Numerical Sim-
106 ulations are typically unfeasible even for laboratory scale plumes, Large-Eddy
107 Simulations (LES) of bubble plumes have been conducted ([21], [22], [23]) using
108 finite-difference or finite-volume discretizations to explicitly resolve the largest,
109 most energetic scales while parametrizing sub-grid scales by Smagorinsky mod-
110 els. In this work the approach is slightly different: instead of low-order spatial

111 discretizations, we use high-order spectral element methods characterized by
112 exponential convergence. In lieu of explicit Smagorinsky models, the specifics
113 of which are still uncertain for bubbly flows [24], we adopt an alternate ap-
114 proach based on spectral filtering [25], [26]. Progressive filtering of the highest
115 modes of the Legendre polynomial approximations is equivalent to a hypervis-
116cosity subgrid-scale model whose influence is explicitly confined to near-grid
117 scale processes [27], [28]. This approach has been shown to maintain spectral
118 accuracy with increasing resolution and provide resolution independent solu-
119 tions. The computational efficiency afforded permits the explicit resolution of
120 a larger range of spatial scales.

121 For large-scale plumes, adequate turbulence resolution, in reasonable time,
122 on available computational resources requires both limiting the vertical extent of
123 the domain and simplifying the full multiphase equation set. Starting from the
124 conservation equations for multiphase systems, following [29], we derive a simpli-
125 fied, Boussinesq model by neglecting the momentum carried by the gas which is
126 much smaller than that of the liquid phase. Even with this simplification, open
127 questions remain concerning the details of dispersed phase modelling of liquid-
128 gas systems. Bubbles in a turbulent flow can be subjected to a wide variety of
129 phenomena that may significantly affect the overall dynamics. Bubble breakup
130 and coalescence, bubble oscillation and rotation and other bubble-bubble and
131 bubble-liquid interactions have been explicitly modeled as *bubble induced* tur-
132 bulence [30], [31], [32], [33]. Although there are numerical studies devoted to
133 understanding the physics behind these processes ([34], [35], [36], [37]), proper
134 parameterization and modeling remains unclear [29]. In a typical environmental
135 blowout, with reasonably small gas volume fractions at the inlet, effects associ-
136 ated with individual bubbles are expected to be small given the levels of local
137 shear produced by the large buoyancy flux at the inlet and the expected small
138 bubble diameters [38]. Accordingly, we argue that the most relevant parame-
139 ter in the first order physics of dispersed bubbles is the slip velocity of the gas
140 phase relative to the liquid. Here we simply set this parameter to a constant
141 value consistent with that reported in experimental plumes [39], [40], numerical

142 simulations [33] and estimations of the rise velocity for gas bubbles during the
 143 DwH spill [41].

144 The current model, with relatively minor modifications, can be used for a
 145 wide range of oceanographic multiphase plume problems. In particular, and
 146 perhaps most importantly, oil phase buoyancy contributions can be explicitly
 147 divorced from the thermal field by considering a mixture model for the liquid
 148 phases. Physicochemical effects can be modeled via evolving distributions of
 149 slip velocities ([40]) and extensions to the study of multiple intrusions in the
 150 water column ([7], [42], [15]) and rotating systems ([43], [44]) are possible.

151 2. Mathematical model

152 2.1. Multiphase plumes

153 Equations describing the evolution of a mixture of fluids, each member of
 154 which is denoted by the subscript k , are introduced. By expressing in the
 155 continuum limit the transport equations obtained using the Volume of Fluid
 156 approach [45], we avoid here the subtleties of working with discrete phases in
 157 deriving a set of partial differential equations [22].

158 The mass conservation equation for phase k can be written as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_k \rho_k) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_k \rho_k \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k) = 0, \quad (1)$$

159 where t is time and ρ_k , α_k and $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k = [\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{w}]_k$ are density, volume fraction
 160 and Cartesian velocity field for the phase k respectively. The assumption of
 161 continuous phase distributions is implicit in (1).

162 Similarly, the momentum equation for the phase k is

$$\frac{D}{Dt} (\alpha_k \rho_k \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k) = -\alpha_k \nabla p + \nabla \cdot \alpha_k \boldsymbol{\tau}_k + \alpha_k \rho_k \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{M}_k, \quad (2)$$

163 where p is pressure, usually taken to be equal in each phase [46], $\nabla \cdot \alpha_k \boldsymbol{\tau}_k$
 164 are the molecular and turbulent diffusive terms for phase k , $\mathbf{g} = -9.8\hat{\mathbf{k}} \text{ m s}^{-2}$
 165 is the gravity acceleration vector aligned with the vertical coordinate z and

166 $D/Dt = \partial/\partial t + \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \nabla$ stands for the material derivative. Any momentum
 167 transfer between phases is accounted in the \mathbf{M}_k term and we require

$$\sum_k \mathbf{M}_k = 0, \quad (3)$$

168 i.e. viscous interactions within the fluid do not affect the bulk momentum.

169 In this work it is assumed that there are only liquid and gas phases identified
 170 as $k = l, b$ respectively. Therefore, for a two-phase plume $\alpha_l + \alpha_b = 1$ and
 171 $\mathbf{M}_l = -\mathbf{M}_b$. The bubble plume forms when the gas phase is injected as a
 172 continuous stream into the liquid phase. The bubbles rise through the liquid
 173 column faster than the liquid due to the lower density of the gas. The difference
 174 between the velocities of the two phases is known as the slip velocity $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s$, i.e.

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l. \quad (4)$$

175 The gas at the well head is dominantly methane which at 1200 m is approx-
 176 imately $\rho_b = 80 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, as compared to seawater at $\rho_0 = 1050 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. During
 177 ascent, the pressure on the bubble changes dramatically. Approximating the
 178 gas state equation by the ideal gas law results in an expansion of the bubble
 179 that may alter the value of the slip velocity [40]. For much of the fluid column
 180 this is a small effect. For example, moving from 1000 m to 500 m reduces the
 181 pressure by half, resulting in a radial expansion of $2^{1/3} \approx 1.3$. At the same time,
 182 the methane will dissolve into the seawater and be consumed by microbes [47],
 183 effects that will reduce bubble volume. Biogeochemistry effects [48] are not con-
 184 sidered explicitly in this work and instead the gas slip velocity is assumed to be
 185 constant. In any case, gas density is small relative to fluid density, $\rho_b/\rho_0 \ll 1$.

186 In these simulations, we adopt a simple seawater equation of state

$$\rho_l = \rho_0 + \rho'_l = \rho_0 [1 - \beta(T - T_0)], \quad (5)$$

187 where the T and ρ'_l stand respectively for temperature and liquid density fluc-
 188 tuation with respect to the reference state, T_0 and ρ_0 , corresponding to the

189 unperturbed seafloor conditions. $\beta = 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ K}$ is the sea water thermal ex-
 190 pansion coefficient. This is only for convenience; extensions to full equations of
 191 state are straightforward. It is also useful to write the temperature T as

$$T = \theta + T_0 + \Gamma(z), \quad (6)$$

192 where θ represents the temperature anomaly obtained after subtracting the
 193 background stratification profile $T_0 + \Gamma(z)$. In this work we assumed a linear
 194 profile $\Gamma(z) = \zeta z$ with slope $\zeta = 0.05 \text{ K m}^{-1}$. Typical stratification slopes are
 195 $\mathcal{O}(0.01 \text{ K m}^{-1})$ [49]. Thus, the equation of state (5) for seawater is

$$\rho_l = \rho_0 [1 - \beta(\theta + \zeta z)]. \quad (7)$$

196 2.2. Mass conservation for the liquid phase

197 Although volume gas fractions may be significant at the well head, it is
 198 assumed that they reach low values rapidly so that $\alpha_l = 1 - \alpha_b \approx 1$ and (1) can
 199 be written as

$$\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l \approx 0, \quad (8)$$

200 where the validity of the above can be assessed by adding the mass conservation
 201 for the two phases

$$\nabla \cdot (\alpha_l \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_b \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b) = 0. \quad (9)$$

202 Rearranging terms and assuming bubbles slip only in the vertical, (9) becomes

$$\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l \approx -w_s \frac{\partial \alpha_b}{\partial z}. \quad (10)$$

203 Typical DwH plume velocities were $\mathcal{O}(1 \text{ m s}^{-1})$ [2] and the plume lateral scales
 204 were meters. Bubble volume fractions reduce from 0.5 to very small values over

205 a few hundred meters, so a conservative estimate of the scale error implied by
 206 the above is

$$\frac{w_s \alpha_{b,z}}{\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l} \approx \frac{0.2 \text{ m s}^{-1} 0.5}{200 \text{ m}} \frac{10 \text{ m}}{1 \text{ m s}^{-1}} = .05 \ll 1. \quad (11)$$

207 *2.3. Seawater Momentum*

208 Summing the momentum equations for each phase yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D}{Dt} (\alpha_l \rho_l \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) + \frac{D}{Dt} (\alpha_b \rho_b \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b) &= -\nabla p + \\ \nabla \cdot \alpha_l \boldsymbol{\tau}_l + \nabla \cdot \alpha_b \boldsymbol{\tau}_b &+ \alpha_l \rho_l \mathbf{g} + \alpha_b \rho_b \mathbf{g}, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

209 where by definition $\sum_k \mathbf{M}_k = 0$. Assuming that bubbles carry a negligible
 210 amount of momentum, reflecting their very small masses relative to seawater,
 211 (12) can be approximated as

$$\frac{D}{Dt} (\alpha_l \rho_l \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \alpha_l \boldsymbol{\tau}_l + \alpha_l \rho_l \mathbf{g}. \quad (13)$$

212 Adopting a traditional Boussinesq approach given that $\rho'_l / \rho_0 = (1 - \alpha_b) \beta (T -$
 213 $T_0) \lesssim 0.15$, the final seawater momentum equations read

$$\rho_0 \frac{D \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l}{Dt} = -\nabla p + \rho_0 \mathbf{g} + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_l - \underbrace{\alpha_b \rho_0 \mathbf{g}}_{\text{bubble}} - \underbrace{\rho_0 \beta (T - T_0) \mathbf{g}}_{\text{thermal}}, \quad (14)$$

214 where the term $\alpha_b \rho'_l = -\alpha_b \rho_0 \beta (T - T_0)$ has been neglected ($|\alpha_b \rho'_l| / \rho_0 \lesssim 2\%$).

215 Introducing our temperature decomposition, (14) becomes

$$\rho_0 \frac{D \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l}{Dt} = -\nabla \tilde{p} + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_l - \underbrace{\alpha_b \rho_0 \mathbf{g}}_{\text{bubble}} - \underbrace{\rho_0 \beta \theta \mathbf{g}}_{\text{thermal}}, \quad (15)$$

216 where the pressure term has been redefined as $\nabla \tilde{p} = \nabla p - \rho_0 \mathbf{g} (1 - \beta \zeta z)$.

217 Note that in (15) there are two contributions to the buoyancy force, one
 218 due to the presence of bubbles (*bubble*) and another one due to temperature
 219 gradients in the liquid phase (*thermal*).

220 *2.4. Gas Slip Velocity*

221 Momentum conservation (2) for gas is

$$\frac{D}{Dt}(\alpha_b \rho_b \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b) = \nabla \cdot \alpha_b \boldsymbol{\tau}_b - \alpha_b (\nabla \tilde{p} + \rho_0 \mathbf{g} - \rho_0 \mathbf{g} \beta \zeta z) + \alpha_b \rho_b \mathbf{g} - \mathbf{M}_b, \quad (16)$$

222 where the term $\rho_0 \mathbf{g} \beta \zeta z$ is negligible ($\frac{\rho_0 g \beta \zeta z}{\rho_0 g} \approx 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for $\zeta = 0.05 \text{ K m}^{-1}$ and
223 $z = 30 \text{ m}$ which is the extent of the computational domain considered here).

224 Note the explicit appearance of the interphase momentum transfer \mathbf{M}_k in (16).

225 Neglecting bubble inertia (consistent with their small mass) and internal gas
226 friction, (16) can be approximated by

$$\mathbf{M}_b = -\alpha_b \rho_0 \mathbf{g}. \quad (17)$$

227 Gas/seawater momentum exchange is typically modeled using a drag law [48],
228 i.e.

$$\mathbf{M}_b = -\frac{3}{4} \alpha_b \rho_0 \frac{C_D}{d_b} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s |\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s|, \quad (18)$$

229 where C_D is the drag coefficient and d_b is bubble diameter. With $C_D = 0.47$
230 for an sphere in a turbulent flow [50] and $d_b = 2 \text{ mm}$,

$$w_s = \sqrt{\frac{4g d_b}{3C_D}} \approx 0.23 \text{ m/s} \quad (19)$$

231 which is in agreement with the experimental slip velocities reported in [39] and,
232 importantly, with the typical values for the DWH [41]. Given the large Reynolds
233 number expected at the inlet for deep water blowouts it is reasonable to assume
234 here a uniform bubble distribution and therefore a unique slip velocity value [40].

235 The above replaces the momentum equation for the second phase, a considerable
236 simplification and practical computational aid.

237 *2.5. Mass conservation of gas*

238 The mass conservation for gas is

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \alpha_b \rho_b + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_b \rho_b \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b) = 0, \quad (20)$$

239 where the gas phase velocity can be written as $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_d$ where $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_d$ is
 240 the drift velocity [51]. This term has been used to account for the interaction
 241 between bubbles and the influence of the liquid phase turbulence that is missed
 242 in the single bubble in a stagnant fluid model in (18). By rewriting $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_d$ using
 243 the classical turbulent viscosity approach one may parametrize this enhanced
 244 turbulent transport due to the presence of bubbles. However such closures are
 245 still far from being conclusive [29].

246 In this work the bubble model was intended to be kept as simple as possi-
 247 ble and no parametrization for additional turbulent transport has been used.
 248 Therefore, the gas phase slip $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b$ is simply approximated as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_b = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_s - \mathcal{D}_b \frac{\nabla \alpha_b}{\alpha_b}, \quad (21)$$

249 where \mathcal{D}_b is taken to be a constant diffusivity coefficient and (20) yields

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_b}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_b \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) = \mathcal{D}_b \nabla^2 \alpha_b - w_s \frac{\partial \alpha_b}{\partial z}. \quad (22)$$

250 2.6. Energy conservation

251 The seawater temperature equation is

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (T \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) = \mathcal{D}_\theta \nabla^2 T, \quad (23)$$

252 where \mathcal{D}_θ is taken to be a constant diffusivity coefficient. The diffusivity and
 253 slip velocity are the only differences between the two active scalars T and α_b ,
 254 although molecular diffusion will be demonstrated to have a negligible impact.

255 Using the decomposition in (6), (23) yields

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\theta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) = \mathcal{D}_\theta \nabla^2 \theta - w_l \zeta. \quad (24)$$

256 The transport equations can be then non-dimensionalized using a veloc-
 257 ity, length and temperature scales U_s , L_s and θ_s respectively. Denoting non-
 258 dimensionalized variables using the same symbols as the dimensional ones above,

259 the final set of transport equations may be written

$$\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l = 0, \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{D\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l}{Dt} = -\nabla\tilde{p} + \frac{1}{Re}\nabla^2\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l + Ri_b\alpha_b\hat{\mathbf{k}} + Ri_\theta\theta\hat{\mathbf{k}}, \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{\partial\alpha_b}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_b\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) = \frac{1}{Pe_b}\nabla^2\alpha_b - w_s\frac{\partial\alpha_b}{\partial z}, \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\theta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_l) = \frac{1}{Pe_\theta}\nabla^2\theta - w_l\zeta^*. \quad (28)$$

260 The non-dimensional parameters are the Reynolds number, $Re = U_s L_s / \nu$,
 261 the bubble and thermal Péclet numbers, $Pe_b = U_s L_s / \mathcal{D}_b$ and $Pe_\theta = U_s L_s / \mathcal{D}_\theta$
 262 respectively, and the bubble and thermal Richardson numbers, $Ri_b = g L_s / U_s^2$
 263 and $Ri_\theta = \beta \theta_s g L_s / U_s^2$ respectively. Finally, $\zeta^* = \zeta L_s / \theta_s$ is the non-dimensional
 264 stratification slope.

265 2.7. Model Summary

266 Equations (25)-(28) form a closed set for computing the dynamic evolution
 267 of multiphase buoyant plumes driven by the density defect due to the presence
 268 of gas. Considering the mixture (liquid and dispersed bubble phase) momen-
 269 tum eliminates the need for explicit models of interphase stresses. Due to the
 270 very large difference in liquid and gas densities, the contribution of the gas
 271 phase to the mixture momentum can be neglected and, following the Boussi-
 272 nesq assumption (strictly valid only for small inlet gas volume fractions), density
 273 fluctuations due to bubbles appear only as a buoyancy force [29]. As such, the
 274 liquid phase velocity is non-divergent and closure requires an evolution equation
 275 for the gas phase volume fraction. The gas phase continuity equation can be
 276 written in terms of the computed liquid velocity and the relative (slip) velocity
 277 between the phases. For bubble flows (plumes, bubblers and aeration columns),
 278 the value of this parameter is typically found from semi-empirical fitting of the

279 terminal rise velocity of single bubbles ([29], [34], [32], [52]). Since the rise ve-
280 locity depends primarily on bubble size, the slip velocity is assumed constant for
281 mono-disperse bubble distributions, consistent with experimental observations
282 [39].

283 The major limitations of the model for investigating deepwater blowouts in-
284 volve (a) the need for relatively small values of inlet gas volume fraction (the
285 Boussinesq assumption) and (b) the lack of explicit physico-chemical processes
286 (constant slip velocity or constant, monodisperse bubble size). Although obser-
287 vations from the DwH incident have estimated gas volume fractions as high as
288 50% at the inlet [2], intense entrainment will lead to rapid decay of the scalar.
289 In addition, assuming incompressibility of the gas phase, strict validity of the
290 Boussinesq approximation requires only that the vertical gradient of the gas vol-
291 ume fraction be small (see Eq. 11). As such, we expect this model assumption
292 to be reasonable at small downstream distances, in fully-developed plumes for
293 even larger values of inlet gas volume fraction than those considered here.

294 Modelling the slip velocity as a single constant implies a mono-disperse and
295 constant bubble size distribution. In the absence of consumption and dissolu-
296 tion, individual gas bubbles should expand while rising, leading to an increased
297 slip velocity. Very deep in the fluid, this expansion is extremely slow to oc-
298 cur. For example, moving from 1500m to 1000m involves a radial expansion
299 of roughly 10%. Of course, there really is some degree of consumption and
300 dissolution, so the actual expansion would be reduced. In a sense, a constant
301 slip velocity roughly parameterizes consumption, dissolution and gas compress-
302 ibility. The value of the slip velocity used here is consistent with experimental
303 values for bubble sizes $\sim 2\text{mm} \leq d_b \leq \sim 8\text{mm}$ and corresponds to estimates
304 previously used for the DwH plume [41].

305 *2.8. Integral models*

306 Buoyant plumes and jets have been extensively studied using integral solu-
307 tions first derived by Morton *et al.* [4] and later extended to bubble plumes
308 by Milgram [6] and others. In these solutions the entrainment per unit length

309 into the edge of the plume is characterized by representative local velocity and
 310 length scales, $\overline{W}(z)$ and $b(z)$ respectively, so that $(rU)|_\infty = -\alpha b \overline{W}$ where α is
 311 the entrainment coefficient and U and W are mean radial and vertical velocity
 312 components respectively.

Assuming Gaussian profiles for the mean vertical velocity $W(r, z) = \overline{W}(z)e^{-(r^2/b(z))^2}$,
 the volume, momentum and buoyancy flux, Q , M and B respectively, can be
 written as

$$Q = \int_0^\infty W r dr = \frac{1}{2} b^2 \overline{W}, \quad (29)$$

$$M = \int_0^\infty W^2 r dr = \frac{1}{4} b^2 \overline{W}^2, \quad (30)$$

$$B = \int_0^\infty W g' r dr = B_\theta + B_b, \quad (31)$$

313 where $g' = g \Delta\rho/\rho_0$ is the reduced gravity, g is the gravity acceleration and
 314 $\Delta\rho = \rho_e - \rho$ where $\rho_e(z) = \rho_0(1 - \beta\zeta z)$ is the unperturbed environment density
 315 profile and ρ is the density in the plume. This term can be rewritten as $\Delta\rho/\rho_0 =$
 316 $\beta\theta + \alpha_b - \alpha_b(\rho_b - \rho'_i)/\rho_0$ where the last term, following previous approximations,
 317 has been neglected.

Thus, the thermal B_θ and bubble B_b buoyancy fluxes are defined as

$$B_\theta = \int_0^\infty W g \beta \Theta r dr, \quad (32)$$

$$B_b = \int_0^\infty W g \langle \alpha_b \rangle r dr, \quad (33)$$

318 where $\Theta = T - (T_0 + \zeta z)$ is the mean temperature perturbation (obtained by
 319 subtracting the stratification mode) and $\langle \alpha_b \rangle$ is the mean gas volume fraction.
 320 Gaussian profiles are also assumed for $\Theta = \overline{\Theta}(z) \exp(-r^2/b(z)^2)$ and $\langle \alpha_b \rangle =$
 321 $\overline{\alpha_b}(z) \exp(-r^2/(\lambda b(z))^2)$ where the parameter λ is the ratio of the gas volume
 322 fraction to momentum plume widths.

323 Using the previous definitions and the transport equations described in sec-
 324 tion 2, the integral model equations read

$$\frac{dQ}{dz} = 2\alpha M^{1/2}, \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{dM}{dz} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{Q}{M} \left(B_\theta + \frac{\lambda^2 + 1}{2} B_b \right), \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{dB_\theta}{dz} = -N^2 Q, \quad (36)$$

$$\frac{dB_b}{dz} = -g \frac{d}{dz} \int_0^\infty w_s \alpha r dr, \quad (37)$$

325 where γ is the momentum amplification factor defined as the ratio of the total
 326 momentum flux to the momentum flux carried by the mean flow and N is the
 327 buoyancy frequency defined as $N = \sqrt{-(g/\rho_0) \partial \rho_e / \partial z} = \sqrt{\beta g \zeta}$.

328 For $w_s \neq 0$, the system in (34)-(37) is unclosed. While this has been cir-
 329 cumvented by hydrostatic assumptions [53], even a constant slip velocity breaks
 330 self-similarity in the same way as a non-zero stratification. When $w_s/w_0 \ll 1$,
 331 the gas phase contribution can be ignored as in [54] and the system defined
 332 by Equations (34)-(37) is closed ($B_{b,z} = 0$). Note that in the Integral Models
 333 (Equations (34)-(37)) the effect of bubbles on the turbulence is only accounted
 334 in the momentum Equation (35) through the γ parameter which is known to be
 335 larger in multiphase plumes due to turbulent mixing enhancement associated to
 336 the presence of a gas phase [6]. Thus, the turbulent transport of temperature or
 337 gas volume fraction is not explicitly accounted in Equations (36) and (37). How-
 338 ever, even for single phase plumes in unstratified environments ($\zeta = 0$), where
 339 the integral solutions would predict a constant buoyancy flux B ($B_{,z} = 0$), this
 340 value should actually decrease due to the turbulent mixing.

341 **3. Computational Test Case**

342 *3.1. Plume parameters*

343 We consider three plumes differentiated only by the ratio of active scalar
 344 contributions to the inlet buoyancy flux: a purely thermal, a (almost) purely
 345 bubble and a hybrid case. In each case, the inlet buoyancy flux is fixed to
 346 the order of magnitude estimated for the DwH spill, $B_{DwH} = g \Delta \rho_0 w_0 A / \rho_0 =$

347 $0.37 \text{ m}^4 \text{ s}^{-3}$, where $D = 0.5 \text{ m}$ is the source diameter, $w_0 = 1.3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is the
 348 inlet liquid phase velocity and $A = \pi D^2/4 \approx 0.2 \text{ m}^2$ is the inlet cross section
 349 area. This is thermally equivalent to $B_0 = \rho_0 C_p B_{DwH}/(\beta g) = 0.8 \text{ GW}$, where
 350 $C_p = 4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is the heat capacity of sea water.

351 This fixed inlet buoyancy flux B_{DwH} can be distributed over either or both
 352 of the thermal δB_θ^0 and gas phase $(1 - \delta)B_b^0$ fractional contributions where
 353 $B_\theta^0 = g A w_0 \beta \Delta T_0$ and $B_b^0 = g A w_0 \alpha_{b,0}$. $\alpha_{b,0}$ is the gas volume fraction at the
 354 inlet and ΔT_0 is the inlet temperature difference with respect to the seafloor
 355 reference state. Here the gas phase buoyancy flux is the *dynamic* flux based on
 356 the liquid phase velocity, w , in contrast to the *kinematic* flux based on $(w + w_s)$.
 357 This ensures that the input momentum forcing is identical for all plumes. Table
 358 1 summarizes the three cases studied: bubble (B), hybrid (H) and thermal (T).
 359 An additional case (H2), with only 10% of the buoyancy flux due to the presence
 360 of bubbles, has also been considered to gain more insight on the dependency
 361 of the turbulence enhancement on the inlet gas volume fraction. To match
 362 expectations in a deep-water release, the effluent in all cases is substantially
 warmer than the ambient fluid.

Case	Plume description	δ	$\alpha_{b,0}$	$\Delta T_0 (K)$
T	Thermal	1	-	746
B	Bubble	0.05	0.142	37
H	Hybrid	0.5	0.075	373
H2	Hybrid 2	0.9	0.015	671

Table 1: Summary of the cases

363

364 3.2. Computational model

365 The transport equations, (25)-(28) are solved using the Spectral Element
 366 Method (SEM) code Nek5000 [55]. This code has been validated for a wide range
 367 of flow configurations and has demonstrated excellent scalability on parallel

368 machines. SEM overcomes the limitation of the classic fully-spectral methods
369 in terms of restricted type of boundary conditions and geometry allowing high-
370 order solutions for complex grids [56].

371 Here we make use of the spectral accuracy and scalability of Nek5000 to per-
372 form highly resolved simulations. Instead of a typical LES approach explicitly
373 modelling subgrid scales via variations of Smagorinsky eddy diffusivities [57],
374 [58], we use the Spectral Vanishing Viscosity [25] technique where the near-
375 grid scale coefficients of the spectral polynomial expansion are progressively
376 filtered [28],[56]. This is equivalent to increasing the nominal Reynolds and
377 Péclet numbers only at near-grid scales. Specifically, the current results use a
378 5% polynomial filtering of the two highest modes in the 12th order Legendre
379 expansion for all computed fields. This procedure preserves the exponential
380 convergence of the spectral solver while avoiding the cost of computing SGS co-
381 efficients. Results using this approach in the context of turbulent channel flow
382 show excellent agreement with DNS, relative insensitivity to the filter shape and
383 overall computational efficiency [26].

384 The computational domain, shown in Fig. 1, is a cylinder of radius $R/D = 25$
385 and height $L_z/D = 60$ ($R = 12.5$ m and $L_z = 30$ m). The domain is decomposed
386 into $K = 12544$ elements and the solution on each element is approximated
387 using 12th order Legendre polynomials for a total number of degrees of freedom,
388 $N_T \approx 22$ million. Typical spatial resolution near the axis of the plume is 0.02 m
389 increasing to 0.3 m in radial far-field.

390 Dirichlet boundary conditions specifying top hat profiles of velocity and
391 scalar fields at the circular inlet are implemented on the lower boundary. On
392 lateral boundaries, perturbation temperature and gas volume fraction are set to
393 zero. To allow the entrainment of fresh fluid into the domain, open boundary
394 conditions are used for the momentum on the sides. Similar conditions, imposed
395 at the top, allow dynamic outflow of the plume. To smooth fluctuations in the
396 fields in the vicinity of the open boundary conditions, numerical sponges are
397 implemented over $r/D \geq 20$ and $z/D \geq 42.5 = z_{max}$. The Region of Interest
398 (ROI), defined as the unperturbed computational domain, extends over $z/D \leq$

Figure 1: A sketch of the computational domain showing an instantaneous isosurface of vertical velocity extending over the domain. The mesh at $z = 0$ shows the boundaries of the spectral elements. Top and lateral shaded areas show the approximate extent of the numerical sponges.

399 42.5 and $r/D \leq 20$. To ensure that the sponges do not alter results in the ROI, a
 400 comparison between the domain described above and one extended to $z/D = 80$
 401 in the vertical was performed and resulted in no significant differences.

402 Table 2 shows the set of parameters used in this work. The velocity U_s ,
 403 length L_s and temperature θ_s scales are set to be the injection velocity w_0 ,
 404 the pipe diameter D and the bottom to top background seawater temperature
 405 difference ($\theta_s[\text{K}] = \zeta z_{max} L_s$) respectively. For each case in Table 1 the flow
 406 was evolved in time until steady values of volume integrated quantities (total
 407 scalar mass as well as the kinetic and potential energies) were achieved.

408 For all cases the initial conditions were zero velocity and scalar (α, θ) fields.
 409 Once the flow was fully developed, statistics were computed by averaging in
 410 time over a period $\Delta\tau = 250D/w_0$. For the axisymmetric plumes, statistical
 411 sampling was increased by additional averaging over $N_\phi = 200$ azimuthal points.
 412 Longer time samplings did not exhibit significant differences for the mean and
 413 second order quantities considered. The simulations were carried out on a Cray

$w_0(\text{m/s})$	$D(\text{m})$	$\theta_s(\text{K})$	$w_s(\text{m/s})$	w_s/w_0	Re	Pr	Sc	Ri_b	Ri_θ	ζ^*
1.3	0.5	1.062	0.23	0.18	13,000	7.0	1.0	2.9	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.023

Table 2: Plume simulation parameters

414 XE6 using 960, 2.2 GHz AMD Magny-Cours cores. The CPU time to achieve
415 the reported statistical sampling was approximately 300,000 core hours for each
416 case.

417 4. Results

418 The plumes are forced by identical inlet momentum and buoyancy fluxes.
419 Consequently, any observed differences between the evolution of single and mul-
420 tiphase plumes is entirely due to the slip velocity of the gas phase. In the present
421 cases, the imposed slip velocity is only 18% of the injection velocity w_0 , and an
422 even smaller percentage of the maximum vertical velocity produced by the large
423 buoyancy flux. The comparisons, therefore, minimize the differences between
424 the three cases; the three plumes are essentially identical and the sole differen-
425 tial parameter is small in relative terms. This parameter appears only in the
426 conservation equation for the gas phase volume fraction. As we shall show, the
427 difference in the values of the modeled molecular diffusivity of the two scalars
428 is insignificant given the predominance of turbulent mixing.

429 With the instantaneous velocity components given by $(\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{w})$ in cylindrical
430 polar coordinates (r, θ, z) , upper case letters or angle brackets $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denote com-
431 bined temporal and azimuthal averages and lower case letters denote fluctuating
432 quantities; the classic Reynolds decomposition reads, $\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{u}$. For dimen-
433 sional consistency, the active scalar field, s is defined as $s \equiv \beta \theta + \alpha_b$.

434

435 4.1. Mean transport

436 The mean centerline vertical velocity W_c is shown in Fig. 2(a) for the three
437 cases described in Table 1. Close to the source the momentum flux at the inlet

438 generates a buoyant jet that rapidly evolves into a buoyant plume. The transi-
 439 tion location can be estimated using the Morton length scale $L_M = M_0^{3/4} B_0^{-1/2} =$
 440 $1.43D$. Shabbir and George [59] observed that the buoyant plume is established
 441 at $z/L_M > 5$ shown in Fig. 2(a) as a dashed line.

442 Given identical values of the significant inlet momentum flux and the dispar-
 443 ity between the slip and inlet velocities, the maximum vertical velocity in each
 444 case occurs at the same downstream location, $z/D \approx 4$. The effect of the slip
 445 velocity, however, is seen even at this small distance where the maximum value
 446 of vertical velocity increases with increasing gas volume fraction. Beyond this
 447 maximum, the vertical velocity in both multiphase plumes decays significantly
 448 faster than in the single-phase case. Despite a nearly 50% decrease in inlet gas
 449 volume fraction, the decay rate in the hybrid plume closely mimics that of the
 450 bubble plume. The rapid increase in the decay rate of the centerline velocity
 451 suggests that the presence of gas, as modeled here, has a significant impact on
 452 the mixing of momentum in the plume.

453 The downstream evolution of the primary prognostic integral model quanti-
 454 ties, the radially averaged volume and momentum fluxes, are show in Fig. 2(b)
 455 and 2(c). For comparison, each flux is plotted against $(z/z_{max})^{a_i}$ where
 456 $a_Q = 5/3$ and $a_M = 4/3$ are the standard, self-similar values for an unstratified
 457 thermal plume. Although non-zero stratification and slip velocity prevent strict
 458 self-similar evolution of the integral fluxes, for the present parameter values and
 459 vertical domain, the vertical variation in the buoyancy flux (shown by dashed
 460 lines in both rescalings) is small in all cases. The rescaled Q and M fluxes
 461 are nearly linear for $z/D > 20$. $(z/z_{max})^{5/3} \gtrsim 0.3$ and $(z/z_{max})^{4/3} \gtrsim 0.35$
 462 respectively.

463 Fig. 2(b) indicates that the vertical volume flux, and hence the horizontal
 464 entrainment, is initially larger in the single phase plume. However, farther
 465 downstream both multiphase plumes show greater, and nearly identical, slopes
 466 relative to the thermal case. This increase in Q is seen despite the clear decrease
 467 in the growth rate of the momentum flux shown in Fig. 2(c). As such, in terms of
 468 typical integral model parameterizations, the multiphase plumes exhibit larger

469 values, with respect to the thermal plume, of both the entrainment coefficient,
 470 α and the momentum amplification factor, γ .

(a) Mean centerline velocity

(b) Volume flux

(c) Momentum flux

Figure 2: (a): Mean centerlines vertical velocity component W_c for the bubble (case B, black line), thermal (case T, red line) and hybrid (case H, blue line) plumes. $z = 5 L_M$ is indicated as a vertical dashed line. Self-similar solution $W_c \sim z^{-1/3}$ shown as a thin red dashed line. (b): Volume (solid lines) and buoyancy (dashed lines) fluxes for the three cases using the thermal plume scaling, $W_c \sim z^{-1/3}$ where $z_{max}/D = 42.5$. The inset shows a detail of the turnover point in Q for the thermal and hybrid cases. Slope indicated as thin dashed lines. (c): Momentum (solid lines) and buoyancy (dashed lines) fluxes as in (b).

471 While W , Θ and $\langle \alpha_b \rangle$ are not strictly self similar, each quantity is extremely
 472 well fit by Gaussian profiles at any vertical location beyond $z/D \gtrsim L_M/D$.

473 Closer to the source, the imposed top-hat profiles persist. The (half-)width
474 of a general quantity ψ is defined using the standard deviation, σ , in $\psi(r, z) =$
475 $\psi_c(z) \exp(-r^2/\sigma_\psi^2(z))$ where r is the radial coordinate and $\psi_c(z)$ is the centerline
476 value.

477 The radial extent of both the momentum and scalar fields in the three cases
478 is shown in the top row of Fig. 3 using best-fit σ values for momentum (black),
479 gas volume fraction (blue) and temperature (red). In the single phase case,
480 temperature advects with the fluid and the momentum and scalar plumes nec-
481 essarily grow at the same rate. In the absence of stratification, the growth is
482 linear. For multiphase plumes, $\langle\alpha_b\rangle$ is stretched with respect to the momentum
483 in the direction of the slip velocity. This narrowing of the bubble plume is seen
484 in both multiphase cases where the half-widths of $\langle\alpha_b\rangle$ are less than those of
485 W for all values of z . The decrease of the width of the bubble plumes rela-
486 tive to the single phase thermal plume is shown in Fig. 3(d). Both multiphase
487 plumes are initially narrower than the thermal plume. Downstream, $z/D \gtrsim 15$,
488 however, the ratio increases with the same, nearly constant, slope for both the
489 bubble and hybrid cases. Assuming this trend persists, one would expect that
490 the multiphase scalar plumes, despite the narrowing effects of the slip velocity,
491 would eventually be broader than the single phase thermal plume.

492 The narrowing of the buoyancy source by the slip velocity in the multiphase
493 plumes also changes the evolution of the momentum fields. In contrast to the
494 single phase case, the top panel shows nonlinear evolution of both scalar and
495 momentum plume widths in the bubble and hybrid cases. The effect of the
496 slip velocity on the dynamics is quantified by plotting the ratio of the multi to
497 single phase momentum plume widths in Fig. 3(e). In the very near-field, the
498 decrease in the radial extent of $\langle\alpha_b\rangle$ effectively reduces the width of multiphase
499 momentum plumes relative to the single phase results. This initial reduction is
500 compensated downstream by an apparent increase in turbulent mixing resulting
501 in more rapid radial spreading of momentum in the multiphase plumes.

502 As any deep-water release will necessarily involve the combined effects of
503 multiple buoyancy components, it is instructive to examine the differences in

504 the evolution of the two active scalar fields in the present hybrid case. As shown
 505 in Fig. 3(d), the ratio of the bubble to thermal plume widths in the hybrid case
 506 decreases rapidly in the near-field at exactly the same rate as $\sigma_b^B/\sigma_\theta^T$. Unlike
 507 the $\sigma_b^B/\sigma_\theta^T$ ratio, $\sigma_b^H/\sigma_\theta^H$ does not show a rapid downstream increase and the
 508 bubble plume is always narrower than the thermal plume in the hybrid case
 509 (Fig. 3(c)). The momentum, due to equal contributions from each scalar, is
 510 necessarily confined between the two scalar plumes. Comparisons of the width
 511 of the hybrid scalar plumes ($\sigma_b^H, \sigma_\theta^H$) to their ‘pure’ counterparts ($\sigma_b^B, \sigma_\theta^T$) are
 512 shown in Fig. 3(f). The enhanced mixing in the hybrid case with respect to
 513 the purely thermal plume results in faster spread of the temperature field in the
 514 presence of a gas phase. In contrast, the σ_b^H/σ_b^B ratio is approximately constant
 515 for $z/D \gtrsim 15$ reflecting the near uniform vertical offset in the scalar width ratios
 seen in Fig.3(d).

(a) Thermal plume (case T) (b) Bubble plume (case B) (c) Hybrid plume (case H)

(d) Scalar plume width ratios. (e) Momentum plume widths ratios. (f) Hybrid to pure plume width ratios.

Figure 3: Top: thermal (left), bubble (center) and hybrid (right) plumes momentum and scalar widths. Bottom: Selected plume widths ratios.

Figure 4: (a): Entrainment coefficient α . (b): Scalar to momentum plume width ratio λ . (c): Momentum amplification factor γ .

516 As indicated by the vertical evolution of the integral fluxes Q and M , the
517 presence of a gas phase increases the entrainment flux, reduces the momentum
518 growth rate through the momentum amplification factor γ and implies a non-
519 unitary value of the plume width parameter $\lambda = \sigma_s / \sigma_w$. Fig. 4(a) shows the en-
520 trainment coefficient α for the three plumes computed using (34). The evolution
521 of Q , with an initial faster growth for the single phase plume, results in larger
522 values of α for $z/D \lesssim 12$. However, farther downstream, multiphase plumes
523 exhibit larger dQ/dz associated with increased entrainment fluxes. Similar val-
524 ues of dQ/dz for the bubble and hybrid cases lead also to similar entrainment
525 coefficients in the ROI.

526 Using the best-fit values of σ , the vertical dependence of λ for the three
 527 plumes is shown in Fig.4(b). As expected, λ is close to one for the single phase
 528 flow, but smaller for the bubble ($\lambda \sim 0.9$) and the hybrid ($\lambda \sim 0.85$) cases.
 529 While values in the range $0.4 \leq \lambda \leq 1$ have been used in multiphase integral
 530 models, the present values are consistent with those used by Milgram [6] based
 531 on observations of a relatively large-scale, environmental bubble plume.

532 Distinct differences in the turbulence, as parameterized in integral models
 533 by the amplification factor γ defined in (35), are shown in Fig. 4(c). In the
 534 thermal case, the parameter grows rapidly and reaches an arguably constant
 535 value $\lambda \approx 1.1$ in agreement with previous results [60], [61]. In the multiphase
 536 cases, γ values are initially smaller, with less vertical momentum carried by the
 537 turbulence due to the narrowing of the mean velocity field. Downstream, how-
 538 ever, the turbulent contribution to the total momentum increases continually
 539 resulting in non-constant values of γ over the available vertical extent of the
 540 computations.

541 The results obtained for the mean vertical evolution of the modeled plumes
 542 agree with basic experimental observations, namely that the presence of gas
 543 enhances turbulent mixing and thus the spreading rates of bubble plumes. Pa-
 544 rameterization of the gas phase through a simple slip velocity allows decoupling
 545 of the active scalar field from the momentum. This results in differences in the
 546 vertical evolution of the scalar and momentum plumes ($\lambda < 1$). The initial
 547 enhanced concentration of the buoyancy produces larger maximum vertical ve-
 548 locities but also generates increased turbulent transport and mixing resulting in
 549 faster spreading rates than in the single phase case.

550 4.2. Plume turbulence

551 Differences in the turbulence produced by the three plumes can be quantified
 552 by comparing the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE), $K = \frac{1}{2} \langle u_i u_i \rangle$, at two different
 553 vertical locations as shown in Fig. 5(a). At $z/D = 10$ (solid lines) the TKE
 554 increases with increasing inlet gas volume fraction. Defining the radial integral
 555 of K as $I_K = \int_0^\infty K r dr$, the multiphase plumes B, H and H2 exhibit I_K increases

556 of 16%, 7% and 2% respectively relative to the single phase case (see Table 3).
 557 The vertical location of the peak where the maximum value of TKE occurs is the
 558 same for all the cases. At $z/D = 31.5$ (dashed lines) the profile has widened but
 559 the peak still persists showing maximum values only slightly smaller than closer
 560 to the source. The increase in TKE in the multiphase plumes with respect to
 561 the thermal case is now larger; the hybrid and bubble cases, with similar values
 562 of TKE, are 24 – 29% larger respectively. For comparison, case H2 exhibits K
 563 values almost identical to the thermal case in the region close to the axis but
 564 the profile increases along the radial direction eventually becoming similar to
 565 that observed in the other multiphase plumes. With only 10% of the buoyancy
 566 flux due to bubbles, the I_K value in the H2 case is 11% larger than in the single
 567 phase plume.

568 Fig. 5(b) shows the vertical development of the ratio of multiphase I_K to
 569 the single phase case. The bubble plume, with the largest gas volume fraction,
 570 initially exhibits the fastest relative growth of I_K followed by an approximately
 571 constant plateau region. In the hybrid plume, the growth of K occurs at a slower
 572 rate over the entire computational domain. At the end of the ROI both bubble
 573 and hybrid cases exhibit similar values of I_K . For the H2 plume, I_K grows the
 574 slowest reaching values $\sim 10\%$ smaller than in the other two multiphase cases
 575 at the end of the computational domain. This suggests that the production of
 576 TKE with respect to the single phase plume depends strongly, and nonlinearly
 577 on the amount of gas at the inlet.

578 The presence of a gas phase, as modeled here, does not appreciably change
 579 the anisotropy of the turbulence. In all cases, $\langle w^2 \rangle \approx 2\langle u^2 \rangle \approx 2\langle v^2 \rangle$, consis-
 580 tent with classical turbulence predictions for nearly parallel shear flows [62].
 581 Comparisons of the Reynolds stresses, $\langle wu \rangle$, at the same vertical locations are
 582 shown in Fig. 5(c). The results are similar to those found for the TKE: close to
 583 the source the $\langle wu \rangle$ values are ordered according to gas content while farther
 584 downstream, bubble and hybrid plumes are very similar. Again, near the axis,
 585 the Reynolds stress in the small gas volume fraction case is similar to observa-
 586 tions in the single phase plume but the profile approaches the other multiphase

$\int_0^\infty \mathbf{r} \, d\mathbf{r}$	B		H		H2	
	$z/D = 10$	$z/D = 31.5$	$z/D = 10$	$z/D = 31.5$	$z/D = 10$	$z/D = 31.5$
K	1.16	1.24	1.07	1.29	1.02	1.11
$\langle wu \rangle W_{,r}$	1.23	1.06	1.12	1.09	1.03	1.02
$Ri_s \langle ws \rangle$	1.02	1.14	0.98	1.22	0.99	1.07

Table 3: Ratios of some selected integral quantities for the bubble and hybrid cases with respect to the thermal case.

587 profiles as r increases. When compared to the thermal case, the bubble plume
588 shows 16% and 24% increases in $\langle wu \rangle$ at $z/D = 10$ and $z/D = 31.5$ respectively,
very close to the results for the TKE.

Figure 5: (a): Turbulent Kinetic Energy at $z/D = 10$ (solid lines) and $z/D = 31.5$ (dashed lines) for the cases in Table 1. (b): $I_K(z/D)$ for cases B, H and H2 with respect to the single phase case. (c): Reynolds stress $\langle wu \rangle$ as in (a).

589

590 In summary, the proposed model, with no parametrized bubble induced tur-
591 bulence [29], predicts a local increase in TKE of up to $\sim 30\%$ in multiphase
592 plumes compared to the single phase case. This difference is substantial, espe-
593 cially in light of the relatively small value of the slip velocity in the near field for
594 the large inlet buoyancy flux considered. The results suggests that even small
595 amounts of gas affect the turbulence in the plume and that the relationship be-

596 tween the inlet gas volume fraction and the resulting increase in the turbulent
 597 mixing is not linear.

598 4.3. Mechanism for enhanced two-phase turbulence

599 The mechanism by which the slip velocity enhances the turbulent production
 600 can be explained in the context of the TKE budget. Given the results shown
 601 in Fig. 2 we assume local self-similarity over a relatively narrow vertical extent,
 602 $30.4 < z/D < 39.1$. Rescaling the data using $\eta = r/z$, it is possible to evaluate
 603 the different contributions to the budgets of mean momentum, scalar and TKE.

Using this approach, results for the budget of mean vertical momentum,

$$\begin{aligned}
 U \frac{\partial W}{\partial r} + W \frac{\partial W}{\partial z} = & - \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \\
 & - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r \langle uw \rangle)}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial \langle w^2 \rangle}{\partial z} + Ri_\theta \theta + Ri_b \alpha_b,
 \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

604 are shown in Fig. 6(a). The main contributions are the radial turbulent trans-
 605 port, the vertical mean advection and the buoyancy, in agreement with those
 606 reported in [59] for a thermal buoyant plume. The small error, shown as a thick
 607 black line, indicates that the local self-similar approximation is reasonable.

Fig. 6(b) shows the TKE budget

$$\begin{aligned}
 U \frac{\partial K}{\partial r} + W \frac{\partial K}{\partial z} = & - \langle u^2 \rangle \frac{\partial U}{\partial r} - \langle uw \rangle \frac{\partial U}{\partial z} \\
 & - \langle uw \rangle \frac{\partial W}{\partial r} - \langle w^2 \rangle \frac{\partial W}{\partial z} \\
 & - \frac{U}{r} \langle v^2 \rangle + Ri_\theta \langle w \theta \rangle + Ri_b \langle w \alpha_b \rangle - \epsilon - \omega,
 \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

608 where ϵ stands for dissipation and ω accounts for turbulence diffusion plus pres-
 609 sure strain terms which are not explicitly calculated. In all cases, the produc-
 610 tion of K is dominated by the mean shear (mechanical) contribution, $\langle wu \rangle W_{,r}$.
 611 While relatively larger in the presence of a gas phase, direct buoyancy produc-
 612 tion, $Ri_s \langle ws \rangle$, accounts for no more than 20% of the total in terms of radial
 613 integral quantities. At these vertical locations, the advection terms $UK_{,r}$ and
 614 $WK_{,z}$ are also significant. The results are in agreement with the experimental
 615 thermal plume budgets reported in [59].

Figure 6: (a) Mean vertical momentum budget for the bubble, (solid lines), hybrid (dotted lines) and thermal (dashed lines) plumes. (b) Turbulent kinetic energy budget as in (a).

616 In general, the differences between the plumes over the assumed self-similar
617 extent are small in both budgets. In particular, the dominant mechanical TKE
618 production term at $z/D \sim 35$ is only 6% larger in the bubble plume than in
619 the thermal case (see Table 3). The smaller buoyancy contribution, accounting
620 for only a fraction of the total, is 14% larger. The $\sim 25\%$ increase in I_K
621 observed in Fig. 5(b) for $z/D \gtrsim 20$ must therefore result from larger turbulence
622 production closer to the inlet. Fig. 7(a) shows the vertical dependence of the
623 ratio of mechanical and buoyancy production between the bubble and thermal
624 cases. In the region $5 \lesssim z/D \lesssim 18$ the mechanical production in the bubble
625 case is $\sim 24\%$ larger than in the thermal plume. Farther downstream this ratio
626 decays. The radially averaged direct buoyancy production is initially smaller
627 in the bubble case due to the narrowing of the buoyancy source by the slip
628 velocity. Downstream, however, there is a near constant $\sim 18\%$ increase in
629 buoyancy production in the bubble plume.

630 Differences in the mechanical production of turbulence are due to the ini-
631 tial vertical stretching of the buoyancy forcing by the slip velocity. As shown
632 in Fig. 8(a), at $z/D = 10$ the bubble plume exhibits larger shear close to the

Figure 7: (a) Bubble to thermal ratio of the mechanical (blue line) and buoyancy (orange line) production terms. (b) TKE production for the bubble (black line) and thermal (red line) at two different locations $z/D = 10$ (solid lines) and $z/D = 31.5$ (dashed lines).

633 axis leading to larger production (Table 3). The turbulence is advected verti-
 634 cally resulting in larger downstream values of TKE. The enhanced conversion of
 635 mean to turbulent kinetic energy in the near field necessarily reduces the mean
 636 shear. However, the reduction of mean vertical velocity gradients is offset by the
 637 presence of larger Reynolds stresses. As such, by $z/D = 31.5$ the mechanical
 638 production in the bubble plume still exceeds that in the thermal case.

639 While the effects on the mechanical production are dominant, the increase
 640 in direct buoyancy production, $Ri_s \langle ws \rangle$, in the bubble plume can also be linked
 641 to the slip velocity. The production of $\langle ws \rangle$ is given by the turbulent scalar flux
 642 equations

$$\frac{D \langle w \alpha_b \rangle}{Dt} - (Ri_\theta \langle \theta \alpha_b \rangle + Ri_b \langle \alpha_b^2 \rangle) + w_s \left\langle w \frac{\partial \alpha_b}{\partial z} \right\rangle + \epsilon_b = - \left[\langle u \alpha_b \rangle \frac{\partial W}{\partial r} + \langle uw \rangle \frac{\partial \langle \alpha_b \rangle}{\partial r} \right], \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{D \langle w \theta \rangle}{Dt} - (Ri_\theta \langle \theta^2 \rangle + Ri_b \langle \theta \alpha_b \rangle) + \zeta^* \langle w^2 \rangle + \epsilon_\theta = - \left[\langle u \theta \rangle \frac{\partial W}{\partial r} + \langle uw \rangle \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial r} \right], \quad (41)$$

643 where ϵ_b and ϵ_θ account for the dissipation, turbulent diffusion and fluctuating

(a) Mean vertical velocity radial gradient (b) Mean scalar radial gradient

Figure 8: Mean vertical velocity W (left) and scalar S (right) at $z/D = 10$ (solid lines) and $z/D = 30.5$ (dashed lines) for the bubble (black lines) and thermal (red lines) plumes.

644 pressure-scalar gradient correlations terms for bubbles and temperature respec-
 645 tively.

646 The two mean production terms in each equation, due to radial gradients
 647 in both the mean vertical velocity and the mean scalar field, are written the
 648 right hand side. Radial profiles of these terms are shown in Fig. 9 at $z/D = 21$.
 649 Both quantities are larger in the bubble case. The stretching of $\langle \alpha_b \rangle$ relative
 650 to Θ produces larger mean gradients as shown in Fig. 8(b). As a result, the
 651 relative contribution to the production of $\langle ws \rangle$ from the mean scalar gradient
 652 is considerably increased in the bubble case. Additionally, the stratification
 653 provides a negative-definite contribution to the production of $\langle w\theta \rangle$ while the
 654 slip velocity produces direct contributions to the production of $\langle w\alpha_b \rangle$ via the
 655 indefinite correlation $\langle w \frac{\partial \alpha_b}{\partial z} \rangle$.

656 5. Conclusions

657 It is well known that the presence of a gas in multiphase plumes increases
 658 turbulence mixing, entrainment and spreading rates with respect to single phase,
 659 thermal cases. Here, turbulence resolving computations are used to examine the

Figure 9: Buoyancy production contributions for the bubble (left) and thermal (right) plumes at $z/D = 21$.

660 mechanisms for this difference in dynamics and to quantify its extent in the con-
 661 text of deep water blowouts with inlet buoyancy fluxes much larger than those
 662 typically found in experiments. To clearly isolate the role of a dispersed gas
 663 phase on the dynamics, we derive a parsimonious bubble model directly from
 664 the governing equations under Boussinesq assumptions. The resulting model
 665 contains only a slip velocity as input and avoids any explicit parameterization
 666 of bubble-induced turbulence. Simplification of the system to a single momen-
 667 tum equation allows feasible explicit computations of the near-field turbulence
 668 over scale ranges commensurate with those of previous and potential deepwater
 669 releases.

670 Using this model, we compute the development of plumes in the idealized
 671 case of two, thermal and gas, buoyancy sources. As such any difference in the
 672 dynamics of single and multiphase plumes are due entirely to the slip velocity of
 673 the gas phase relative to that of the liquid. Comparing flows differentiated only
 674 by the ratio of buoyancy contributions at the inlet, modeled two-phase plumes
 675 are found to produce more turbulence, and thus spread faster than in the purely
 676 thermal case. Despite the simplicity of the model and the small value of the

677 imposed slip velocity relative to that of the plume itself, differences in observed
678 turbulence levels are significant. The relationship between the inlet gas volume
679 fraction and the observed turbulence enhancement is highly non-linear. A 50%
680 reduction in the inlet gas volume fraction produces no significant difference
681 in the multiphase turbulent kinetic energy budgets. Appreciable differences
682 between the single and multiphase plume in terms of turbulence intensities are
683 observed even when gas-phase buoyancy contribution is only 10% of the total.

684 Explicit examination of kinetic energy budgets indicates that turbulent pro-
685 duction is primarily due to mechanical shear while direct production from buoy-
686 ancy sources is a minor contribution. Larger shear production in multiphase
687 cases is associated with the vertical stretching induced by the gas phase slip-
688 ping with respect to the liquid. When compared to a purely thermal plume,
689 the dispersed gas phase necessarily narrows the mean momentum field relatively
690 close to the inlet. This larger mean shear is responsible for the increased conver-
691 sion of mean to turbulent energy responsible for larger entrainment and faster
692 spreading downstream.

693 In the context of integral model formulations, the numerical experiments
694 predict modest increases over purely thermal plumes for the entrainment co-
695 efficient and the expected increase in the ratio of momentum to scalar plume
696 widths in the presence of a gas phase. The narrowing of the bubble plume
697 with respect to the momentum plume is greater in the case of mixed buoyancy
698 sources. The observed parameters are reasonably constant for $z/D \gtrsim 15$ with
699 values falling within the (considerable) range of previous experimental measure-
700 ments in isothermal bubble plumes. Consistent with the explicit quantifications
701 of changes in turbulent characteristics, the vertical behavior of the momentum
702 amplification factor, γ , used to account for turbulence effects in integral mod-
703 els, changes considerably in the presence of a gas phase. In the thermal case,
704 γ equilibrates to a reasonably constant value. In contrast, γ is initially smaller
705 in the gas dominated plume, but continues to grow at all observed downstream
706 locations.

707 The present model can be extended to study turbulent dynamics in more
708 realistic representations of large-scale deep water releases. Using the same ap-
709 proach for the gas phase, it is possible to explicitly account for the presence of
710 oil by considering the evolution of the nearly immiscible mixture of two liquid
711 phases. Separating oil and thermal buoyancy contributions permits detailed
712 evaluation of the effects of stratification on the multiphase system, including
713 the role of turbulent mixing on the location and formation of lateral oil/gas
714 intrusion layers. Additionally, by considering non-uniform slip velocities, or dis-
715 tributions of dispersed gas phases with different slip velocities, one may study
716 bubble interaction and more complex, environmentally dependent biogeochem-
717 ical processes including the investigation of dispersant effects.

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